

CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: TRANSFORMATIVE IMPACT ON A STUDENT OVERCOMING STIGMA IN TEENAGE PREGNANCY

Carren Mhe Embornas-Reusora ¹, Krisha Faye C. Crampatan ², Cherly C. Cordova³

¹*Department of Education, Division of Bukidnon, Kibongkog Integrated School, San Fernando, Bukidnon, Philippines*

²*Department of Education, Division of Bukidnon, Malaybalay City National Science High School, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines*

³*Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13999015>

ABSTRACT

This case study explored transformative impact on a student overcoming stigma in teenage pregnancy through an in-depth analysis of a participant from Malaybalay City National Science High School during the 2023-2024 school year. The study aimed to a) identify the impact of teenage pregnancy on a student; b) investigate the challenges students face during pregnancy; and c) understand how a teenage mother overcomes stigma while continuing her education. Using a qualitative case study approach, the research focused on a 16-year-old student. One-on-one interviews, parental confirmation, classroom observations, and quarterly grades provided data for thematic analysis. The study identified five transformative impacts: 1) family and social factors; 2) education and health influences; 3) physical changes; 4) emotional and mental health impacts; and 5) behavioral and belief systems. Findings highlighted how strong family support mitigated negative outcomes, reducing stress and anxiety for both the student and her child. The study underscores the importance of reproductive health programs, supportive school policies, and open parent-child communication.

Keywords: *Teenage pregnancy, stigma, family, student, factors, transformative impact*

INTRODUCTION

Adolescents often encounter numerous health and social challenges. For example, initiating sexual activity without sufficient knowledge and protective skills increases their risk of unwanted pregnancies. In some Member States, the high rates of early marriage and childbearing contribute to elevated maternal mortality and morbidity, as well as higher neonatal and infant mortality rates among adolescents. Moreover, adolescent pregnancy is linked to a greater risk of health issues such as anemia, STIs, unsafe abortions, postpartum hemorrhage, and mental health disorders like depression. Pregnant adolescents also face adverse social outcomes, such as being forced to leave school, which diminishes their future employment prospects and leads to long-term economic challenges. The unmet need for family planning, particularly for spacing births, is notably high among adolescents.

The WHO advocates for Adolescent Sexual and Reproductive Health to address these challenges and provides technical assistance to Member States in enhancing health care systems to offer Adolescent Friendly Health Services. Many adolescents who require sexual and reproductive health services, such as accurate information, contraception, and STI treatment, find these services either unavailable or delivered in a manner that makes them feel unwelcome and embarrassed. Health services must be attuned to the needs and developmental stages of adolescents to effectively engage them. The WHO promotes Adolescent Friendly Health Services to tackle these issues and facilitate easier access for adolescents to the necessary services (World Health Organization, 2024).

Teenage pregnancy continues to be a major social and public health issue, with profound effects on people as individuals, as families, and as society. Among the numerous issues, teenage pregnancy stands as a significant public health and social issue that continues to pose numerous challenges. The advent of the modern era has brought about unprecedented advancements in technology and digital connectivity, reshaping the way adolescents communicate, access information, and navigate relationships. However, along with these advancements, the modern era has also witnessed a growing concern regarding the factors influencing teenage pregnancy.

According to the United Nations Children's Fund (2022), teenage pregnancy is defined as a pregnancy in girls between the ages of 15–19. Based on a study conducted by the UN Population Fund (2013) they found out that teenage pregnancy also adversely affects future earning potential and leads to lifelong poverty. This impact will continue throughout a teenager's life and will carry over to the next generation. At present, it is one of the pressing issues for Filipino youths. The National Nutrition Council (2016), addresses the alarming rise of teenage pregnancy in the Philippines, which is the highest in the Asia-Pacific region. Key findings include that 13.6% of female teens have begun childbearing, a significant increase over the past decade. Contributing factors include early sexual initiation, with 22% engaging in sex before age 18, and a high percentage of

unprotected sex. The statement highlights that many pregnant teens are nutritionally at risk, particularly those aged under 20. It emphasizes the need for improved access to reproductive health services and comprehensive education on family planning. The document calls for local government units to monitor teen pregnancy cases and implement targeted health and nutrition programs to support adolescent mothers and their children.

Research Questions

This research aimed to investigate the impacts of teenage pregnancy on a student focusing on both the personal and academic challenges she encounters. It seeks to uncover the factors that shape students' awareness and resilience, with the goal of informing strategies to address the complex issue of teenage pregnancy in contemporary society.

1. What is the impact of teenage pregnancy on a student?
2. What challenges do students face during pregnancy?
3. How does a teenage mother overcome stigma while continuing her education?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the methodology, research design, research locale, participants and sampling procedure, data gathering tools, instrumentation, validation, data gathering procedures, and data analysis.

The study aimed to conduct in-depth interviews with a single (1) participant who had experienced teenage pregnancy. The study utilized a single-case design, also known as single-subject design or N-of-1 design, which was a research design specifically used for studying individual case. It involved systematically measuring and analysing the behaviour or outcomes of a single participant over time.

The study was conducted in Malaybalay City National Science High School during the school year 2024-2025. Malaybalay City National Science High School (MCNSHS) was a specialized public high school located in Purok 1, Aglayan, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, Philippines. One of the school's goals was to provide a rigorous academic program for talented and academically inclined students. MCNSHS was a well-known and reputable high school that attracted students from different backgrounds and communities.

The researchers utilized purposive sampling in selecting a relevant participant for the study. One (1) participant, aged 16 years old, currently enrollee of Senior High School, who had experienced teenage pregnancy has been selected based from student's willingness and had been voluntarily agreed to share her experience. The selection of this specific participant was based on specific criteria: she should be between the ages of 13

to 19 years old, a student currently enrolled in either Junior High or Senior High Curriculum and have experienced early pregnancy.

The researchers carefully designed open-ended interview questions to capture the key aspects of teenage pregnancy. These questions were developed to gather detailed and insightful responses from the participant. Prior to the final data collection, a pilot testing phase was conducted by testing it to one participant from a different grade level in the same school to undergo the interview process using the open-ended interview questions. The purpose of the pilot testing was to evaluate the reliability and clarity of the interview questions. Feedback from the pilot participant was collected and analysed to ensure that the questions effectively captured the intended information and were easily understandable.

The interview questions had been validated and refined through the pilot testing; the researchers proceeded with the final data collection phase. After that, a one session of one-on-one interview has been achieved, the researchers approached the parent to ensure data veracity by a confirmation. They also provided a clear explanation of the flow of the interview process and ensured that the participant understood the purpose of the study and their role in it.

The gathered data were then transcribed, coded, and analysed using thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns within the participant's experiences. This study was analysed using a case study approach, a qualitative research method that involved in-depth exploration and analysis of an individual, group, or phenomenon. Moreover, the analysed codes and themes, as well as the findings, have been validated by both the participant and her parent to ensure their accuracy. The researchers also included the classroom observation, and quarterly grades as additional sources to support and validate the gathered data and served as triangulation method.

Furthermore, in conducting this study, we took on the role of interviewer-observer. We guided the discussion while also engaging with the participants during the interview. To ensure the trustworthiness of a qualitative study, Merriam (2009) suggested the following methods: triangulation (using multiple data sources as evidence), member checks (having data providers review the conclusions), saturation (continuous data collection until no new information emerges), peer review (consulting with experts), audit trail (keeping a detailed record of data collection and decision-making), and thick description (providing rich, detailed context for the study).

By employing a case study approach with a single-case design and triangulation method, the data analysis process allowed the researchers to delve into the underlying meanings and structures of the participant's lived experiences. It aimed to provide a deep understanding of the phenomenon of teenage pregnancy and uncover the essential factors that shaped the participant's behaviours, attitudes, and emotions.

RESULTS

Table 1. Thematic Analysis of Family and Social Impact

Objective of the study	Category	Codes	Themes
What is the impact of teenage pregnancy on a student?	Family and social	Relationship secrecy	Parental control
		Parental strictness	Parental control
		Absence of parental guidance	Poor parental concern
		Parental involvement in decision-making	Parental involvement
		Habitual partying	Peer influence
		Social media influence on relationship aspirations and future goals	Social media impact
What are the challenges does student encounter while facing teenage pregnancy?		Depends on the person	Personal choice
		The student thinks about finishing school and the future of her baby	Emotional challenge
		Classmates noticed the changes because the student ate a lot	Social stigma
How does a teenage mother overcome stigma while		Friends were shocked with the pregnancy	Social stigma
		Best friends were supportive	Peer support
		Best friends offered to buy her snacks and offered to be the godparents	Peer support

continuing her education?	Best friends were excited	Peer support
	Teachers were concerned with the student's pregnancy	Peer concern
	Overthinking stopped through the advices of her parents	Coping mechanism
	Her parents care for her and doesn't let her do the chores	Family concern
	Her parents care about the baby's health	Family concern

Table 2. Thematic Analysis of Health and Education Impact

Objective of the study	Category	Codes	Themes
What is the impact of teenage pregnancy on a student?	Health and education	Health awareness for pregnancy	Reproductive health awareness
		Contraceptive for family planning	Reproductive health awareness
What are the challenges does student encounter while facing teenage pregnancy?		Delayed menstruation	Pregnancy symptom
		Fever	Pregnancy symptom
		Lays down in bed all the time	Pregnancy symptom
		Couldn't participate in school activities	Physical limitation
		The student was used to face-to-face classes	Challenges on adapting changes

	Modular classes limited the chances to join school activities and competition	Changes in learning style
	The student missed the feeling of being active in school	Challenges on adapting changes
	Difficulty in balancing responsibilities	Challenges on adapting changes
	Difficulty on maintaining academic performance	Challenges on adapting changes
	Reduced time availability	Challenges on adapting changes
How does a teenage mother overcome stigma while continuing her education?	Took herbal medicine and went for a traditional massage for diagnosis	Alternative pregnancy care
	The folk massager listened to pulse to confirm if the teenager was pregnant	Alternative pregnancy care
	Primary knowledge on avoiding stretchmark during pregnancy	Pregnancy self-care
	Letting partner rub her belly instead	Pregnancy self-care
	Applying lotion when it's itchy	Pregnancy self-care

Table 3. Thematic Analysis on Physical Impact

Objective of the study	Category	Codes	Themes
What is the impact of teenage pregnancy on a student?	Physical		
What are the challenges does student encounter while facing teenage pregnancy?		Hairy tummy	Physical Changes
		Darkening of nape	Physical Changes
		Unable to do activities or chores	Physical limitation
		Become weak	Physical challenges
		Difficulty completing schoolwork	Physical challenges
		Experiencing back pain	Physical challenges
		Repetitive studying	Physical challenges
		Memory lapses	Physical challenges
		Stopping studying due to back pain	Physical challenges
		Pain in stomach	Physical challenges
	Hand pain and numbness	Physical challenges	
How does a teenage mother overcome stigma while			

continuing her education?

Table 4. Thematic Analysis of Mental Health and Emotional Impact

Objective of the study	Category	Codes	Themes
What is the impact of teenage pregnancy on a student?	Mental health and emotional		
What are the challenges does student encounter while facing teenage pregnancy?		The student worries about her future at first.	Emotional challenges
		The student thinks about her future and what ifs on her education and partner.	Emotional challenges
		The student overthinks about the child's future.	Emotional challenges
		Emotional sensitivity	Emotional challenges
		Wanting for companionship	Emotional challenges
		Overthinks about her future during the start of the pregnancy	Emotional challenges
How does a teenage mother overcome stigma while continuing her education?		Thinks positively	Coping mechanism
		Self-meditate to avoid stress	Coping mechanism
		The student overcome it through listening to music	Coping mechanism

	Listening to soft music that brings calm and peace	Coping mechanism
	Doesn't mind the judgements and comments.	Coping mechanism
	Taking a break from module and decided to continue the next day	Coping mechanism
	Overthinking stopped when family members assure the students and advises her to continue because they had her full support	Coping mechanism
	Responsible individual	Coping mechanism
	The student doesn't want to be stressed out	Coping mechanism
	Did not experienced depression during the pregnancy.	Coping mechanism
	Experiences stress sometimes because of her nieces and nephews but handles it.	Coping mechanism
	Securing safeness for unborn baby	Coping mechanism
	Feeling excited	Coping mechanism
	Thinks about the health and well-being of the baby.	Coping mechanism

Table 5. Thematic Analysis of Behavior and Belief Impact

Objective of the study	Category	Codes	Themes
------------------------	----------	-------	--------

What is the impact of teenage pregnancy on a student?	Behavior and belief factor	Awareness of religious opposition to abortion	Religious belief
What are the challenges does student encounter while facing teenage pregnancy?			
How does a teenage mother overcome stigma while continuing her education?		Confirming symptoms through searching online	Information-seeking behavior
		Giving advices to those students to enjoy life to the fullest first	Empathy
		Advice for preparing non-pregnant students for future possibilities and responsibilities	Empathy

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presented student's views and perspectives regarding the impact to family and social factors associated with teenage pregnancy, which were examined. This highlighted the importance of understanding the complex interplay between these impacts and how they could contribute to the occurrence of early pregnancies among students. Family and social played crucial roles in shaping attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours related to pregnancy, as identified by a student who had personally experienced early pregnancy through a one-on-one interview.

“Oo. Pero siguro ang uban kay kuan kanang gaka experience sila ug teenage pregnancy siguro kanang tago-tago lang nila, kanang strict ra kaayo ilang family ana ba...

(Yes, but maybe others experiencing teenage pregnancy might be very secretive and their families are very strict.)

“Oh advice sa akong parents tapos caring na kayo sila, responsible na kay sila sa akoo, dili na sila mga---- dili na kayo sigeg sugo (katawa) preggy naman ko, kuan lang kayo sila basta caring lang kay sila responsible kayo sila sakong health, ang baby sila pay magbadlong saakoo if sigeg inom ug bugnaw (katawa). (Yes, advices from my parents and they are very caring and responsible of my situation, they don't allow me to do chores because I'm pregnant. They are very caring and responsible about my health and my baby. They reprimand me every time I drink cold water)”

The given information implies several critical insights regarding teenage pregnancy and its associated stigma, challenges, and support mechanisms. Firstly, these suggests that the stigma surrounding teenage pregnancy is heavily influenced by relationship secrecy, parental strictness, absence of parental guidance, and social media influences. These codes often lead to themes of parental control, poor parental concern, peer influence, and social media impact, all of which contribute to the students' belief about the causes associated with the increased incidence of early pregnancy. Secondly, the challenges faced by pregnant students are significant and multifaceted. The primary concerns include emotional challenges related to the fear of not finishing school and uncertainty about the baby's future. Additionally, social stigma from classmates and friends further exacerbates the emotional burden, indicating a need for greater social support and understanding within the school environment. Lastly, the journey of teenage mothers in overcoming stigma is greatly aided by the support of friends, family, and teachers. Best friends play a crucial role in providing emotional and practical support, such as offering snacks and volunteering as godparents. Teachers' concern for the students' well-being also contributes positively. Parental support, manifested through advice and practical help, is vital in helping teenage mothers cope with stress and continue their education.

These implications point to the necessity for comprehensive sex education, stronger family engagement, and supportive school environments to mitigate the factors leading to teenage pregnancy and to support pregnant students effectively. Enhanced parental guidance and positive peer support systems are crucial in helping teenage mothers navigate their educational and emotional challenges, thereby fostering a more inclusive and supportive atmosphere for all students.

Furthermore, this was related to the study by Tabei, et. al (2021), which investigated the association between teenage pregnancy and family factors in the Philippines through analysing data extracted from the Philippine National Demographic and Health Survey 2017. Results found that living without either parent significantly increases the likelihood of teenage pregnancy, with odds 4.57 times higher compared to those living with at least one parent. As adolescents' approach 19 years of age, their risk of teenage pregnancy rises, increasing by 2.17 times for each year closer to this age. Surprisingly, knowing about contraception is associated with higher odds of teenage pregnancy, suggesting potential gaps between knowledge and effective contraceptive

use. Larger family sizes also contribute to increased odds of teenage pregnancy, with each additional family member associated with a 1.14 times higher risk. Conversely, higher educational attainment and belonging to the richest wealth quintile are protective factors, significantly reducing the odds of teenage pregnancy. Adolescents with education beyond the secondary level exhibit 0.08 times lower odds, while those in the richest wealth quintile show 0.40 times lower odds compared to their counterparts. These findings underscore the importance of addressing familial, socioeconomic, and educational factors to reduce the incidence of teenage pregnancy effectively.

Table 2 provided insights into the beliefs of students regarding teenage pregnancy, specifically concerning the influence of health and education. It focused on facilitating a deeper understanding of teenage pregnancy determinants through the exploration of codes and themes. Health and education played significant roles in shaping students' beliefs. These codes could have a profound influence on how students perceive and understand the consequences, risks, and prevention of teenage pregnancy. To better understand the context, the researchers provided the continuation of the student's one-on-one interview.

“Ano... it’s hard biya na ano---pag preggy naka tapos then pag preggy naka (pause) nya while ga skwela ka inig manganak ka naa nakay atimanon--- ga skwela japon ka, ano na imong kuan--- (nikatawa) multitasking na kay ka pero pag abot ana tapos dili na kayo ka makalaag uban saimong friends ana kay naa nakay baby (pause) tapos pirme dili na kayo ko dili na siguro kay ko makajoin ug kanang mga activities sa school kay pag activities sa school kay kanang ano ba jud dili pa jud ga kuan--- tagaan ba jud nimog oras biya gyud pag nay mga activities sa school, mag kuan baya jud kag oras tapos sa kuan ug preggy naka naa nakay anak dili naka makahatag ug oras para sa activity sa school kay naa naman saimong anak tanan. (It’s really hard, being pregnant while studying. When you are given birth while studying, you have a baby to take care of. You have to multitask; you can’t go out with friends often. You can’t join school activities anymore because it will take some of your time because you already have a baby. Your time will just be for your baby.”

The mentioned codes, such as health awareness for pregnancy and contraceptives for family planning, provided insights into the primary impacts that students believed were associated with early pregnancy with reproductive health awareness. These codes likely represented the key themes or concepts derived from the data collected in the study. Analysing these codes and themes allowed for a deeper understanding of the specific factors that students perceived as contributing to early pregnancy, particularly in terms of their understanding of reproductive health and the importance of contraception for family planning. Reproductive health awareness empowers individuals to make informed decisions about their sexual and reproductive lives. It equips them with the knowledge and skills necessary to maintain their sexual health, prevent unintended pregnancies, protect themselves from STIs, and seek appropriate healthcare when needed. The codes revealed a spectrum of experiences and challenges faced by pregnant teenagers. Symptoms like delayed menstruation and fever, along with physical limitations such as being bedridden, pointed to early signs of

pregnancy. Seeking alternative pregnancy care, such as herbal medicine and consulting a folk massager for diagnosis, highlighted the diverse approaches to healthcare within certain communities.

Additionally, the codes suggested that pregnant students may struggle with adapting to changes, including limitations in participating in school activities due to their physical condition. Transitioning from face-to-face to modular classes may further exacerbate feelings of isolation and hinder opportunities for engagement in school life. Furthermore, insights into coping mechanisms, like focusing on avoiding stretch marks or involving partners in prenatal care, shed light on the multifaceted experiences of pregnant students as they navigate pregnancy and continue their education. When it comes to how these factors influenced students' lifestyles, codes such as difficulty in balancing responsibilities, difficulty in maintaining academic performance, and reduced time availability indicated the challenges faced by pregnant students in adapting to significant life changes. These challenges likely stemmed from the demands of pregnancy, which may have disrupted their usual routines and required them to juggle multiple responsibilities simultaneously. As a result, pregnant students may have found it challenging to prioritize academic commitments while also managing the physical and emotional demands of pregnancy. This underscores the need for comprehensive support systems and accommodations to assist pregnant students in navigating these difficulties and maintaining their academic progress effectively.

Health and education determinants appear to be related to the study conducted by Maemeko, et.al (2018), which investigated the impact of teenage pregnancy on Grade 7 learners at a school in the Zambezi Region. The findings of this study revealed the reasons why these teenagers get pregnant as follows: lack of parental care and control, lack of some material needs, poor peer guidance, lack of sex education, and the influence of alcohol and drug abuse. The impact of teenage pregnancy on academic performance included poor academic performance after the pregnancy, increased dropout because of pregnancy-related issues, and negative feelings on schooling. A significant number of adolescent female students were at risk of facing the challenges of teenage pregnancy in the study area. School-based reproductive health education and strong parent-daughter relationships are recommended. Moreover, another study conducted by Mathewos and Mekuria (2018), aimed to assess the prevalence of teenage pregnancy and its associated factors among school adolescents of Arba Minch Town. This study revealed high level of teenage pregnancy among school adolescents of Arba Minch Town. A significant number of adolescent female students were at risk of facing the challenges of teenage pregnancy in the study area. School-based reproductive health education and strong parent-daughter relationships are recommended.

Table 3 served as a comprehensive exploration into the intricate experiences of students contending with early pregnancy and the profound ramifications these physical factors exerted on their dual roles as both students and teenage mothers. Delving into the nuances of their encounters, the table elucidated the multifaceted landscape of challenges, limitations, and changes wrought upon the individual's body during the early stages of pregnancy. Through detailed analysis, the table aimed to uncover the complex

interplay between academic responsibilities and the demands of pregnancy, offering a valuable understanding of the impact on these students' lives and education. The continuation of the one-on-one interview is as follows.

“When it comes to kanang physical changes na... kay ano kanang.... hairy na kayo imong tummy (nikatawa) hairy jud kay siya... tapos ano...kanang... gapang ano akong batok dari oh gaitom, gaitom akong batok (When it comes to physical changes, my tummy is now hairy, really hairy, your nape is darkening. My nape is darkening)”

“Kanang... ano (pause) kanang hinhin na kay ko sakong mga lihok, dili nako ga-- - dili jud ko ga alsa ug bug-at (I became really carefully with my actions, I don't lift heavy things)”

“Oo dali rako makalimot magbalik-balik ka... magbalik-balik kag ano--- magbalik-balik kag review (I forget easily, so you have to review repeatedly)”

“Kay pag ano... pag mag... naa koy mga sakit sa likod dili ko magstudy (ngisi gamay) (Because when my back hurts, I don't study)”

“Oo sometimes magsakit akong tiyan, magsakit kanang mag kuan akoang kamot kanang gapaminhod bitaw siya (Yes sometimes, my stomach aches, and sometimes my hand gets numb)”

The codes listed, such as hairy tummy, darkening of the nape, and difficulty completing schoolwork, indicate physical changes and challenges experienced during pregnancy. Other codes like back pain, memory lapses, and hand numbness highlight physical limitations that may hinder academic performance. These findings suggest that pregnant students face a multitude of physical challenges and changes that impact their ability to fulfil their roles as students while also navigating the demands of early motherhood.

The physical challenges and changes experienced by pregnant student carry several important implications. Firstly, educational institutions must prioritize providing access to comprehensive healthcare support tailored to the needs of pregnant students. This can include on-campus clinics, counselling services, and referrals to healthcare professionals specializing in prenatal care. Secondly, offering flexible learning options, such as online courses and modified schedules, is crucial to accommodate the physical limitations of pregnant students while ensuring they can continue their education. Additionally, creating a supportive environment within schools is essential, where educators and peers offer encouragement and assistance to pregnant students, helping them navigate academic and personal challenges. Increasing awareness and understanding of the physical challenges of early pregnancy among stakeholders and developing supportive policies and guidelines further contribute to fostering an inclusive and empowering educational environment for pregnant students. By addressing these

implications, educational institutions can better support pregnant students in achieving their academic goals while managing their health needs.

This conformed to the study conducted by Nettle et al. (2013), examined the physical and psychological development of 599 young women from the National Child Development Study who became mothers before age 20, compared to 599 socioeconomically matched controls. Results revealed future young mothers were lighter than controls at birth and shorter at age 7. They had earlier menarche and accelerated breast development, earlier cessation of growth, and shorter adult stature. Future young mothers had poorer emotional and behavioral adjustment than controls at age 7 and especially 11, and by age 16, idealized younger ages for marriage and parenthood than did the controls.

Table 4 highlights the mental health and emotional factors experienced by a student who has undergone teenage pregnancy, offering insights into her journey of coping with the associated struggles. Through an analysis of codes and themes, the table unveils the emotional hurdles faced by the student as she navigates the dual roles of student and young mother. By delving into these emotional challenges, the table sheds light on the complexities of her experience and highlights the importance of understanding and addressing the mental health needs of pregnant and parenting students. Here are some statements from the student's one-on-one interview that illustrate how she handled the situation.

“(Nagkatawa) Ano medyo--- ano ko kay ha? ingon ko nga--- daghan na mo come sa mind nga basin--- basin dili na katiwas ana ko unsaon nalang pero pagkuan pero kato wa pato kabalo sa akua pa pero pagkabalo sakong parents sila nag advice dayon sila nga “Okay ra na yang” mao to wala dayon sa akua, nawala dayon sa akua kuan nga sige padayon gihapon maningkamot gihapon ta kay naa ang parents gasupport gihapon sa atoa (I think about a lot of things, maybe I will not finish school, but when my parents found out they just said that “it’s okay yang” that’s why I didn’t think about anymore, I just have to continue because my parents are there to support us.)”

“Feel nako kay--- huna-huna na dayon ko ato kay--- sa akong future na dayon. Ano lang, sige ralog paminaw sa music kanang mag bonding mi saamong family, mag istorya2x mi para mawala ang mga (ni smile) ano ang mga overthink ma overthink jud basta ikaw ra usa when it comes to kung ikaw ra isa kay--- musulod to saimong utok mag overthink jud ka nga what if puhon unsa ang future ninyo ana... hmm hmm mag overthink na dayon ka kung ikaw ra usa so... ana ra to sya kay naa man pud akoang family nawala rapud sya dili na sya ma kuan--- kay family muana man sila nga “ Okay rana padayon lang gihapon naa rami pirme” ana.

(I just think about my future at that time. I just listen to music, and bond with my family, we talk often to avoid overthinking. You tend to overthink when you are alone, you overthink what will happen in the future. You overthink a lot when you are alone, but it

won't stay for long because my family is there. They will just say "Just continue Yang, we're just here always.)

"Pagsugod ga overthink ko kay what if inane, what if inana ang future"

It revealed multiple codes such as the student doesn't want to be stressed out, doesn't mind the judgments and comments, did not experience depression during the pregnancy, experiences stress sometimes because of her nieces and nephews but handles it, student worries about her future at first, the student thinks about her future and what ifs on her education and partner, student overthinks about the child's future, student overcome it through listening to music, overthinking stopped when family members assure the students and advises her to continue because they had her full support, emotional sensitivity, wanting for companionship, securing safeness for unborn baby, responsible individual, self-meditate to avoid stress, listening to soft music that brings calm and peace, feeling excited, thinks positively, thinks about the health and well-being of the baby, overthinks about her future during the start of the pregnancy, and taking a break from a module and decided to continue the next day. These codes encompass a range of experiences, from managing stress and anxieties to maintaining her mental health and contemplating the future seeking support from family. The student demonstrates resilience by prioritizing her mental well-being and the welfare of her unborn baby. She remains composed amidst potential judgment and stresses, finding solace in music and self-meditation. Encouragement from family members bolsters her resolve, affirming her decision to persevere with their unwavering support. Despite initial concerns about the future, the student approaches challenges with a positive mindset, focusing on the health and happiness of her child. These coping mechanisms underscore the student's strength and adaptability in navigating the complexities of teenage pregnancy while striving to fulfil her academic and maternal responsibilities.

The implications drawn from the student's coping mechanisms and emotional responses carry significant weight in understanding and supporting pregnant and parenting students. Firstly, the recognition of various coping strategies underscores the importance of providing comprehensive support systems within educational institutions. Schools should prioritize offering resources such as counselling services, peer support groups, and mental health initiatives tailored to the unique needs of pregnant and parenting students. Secondly, the student's ability to maintain a positive outlook and seek solace in self-care activities highlights the critical role of resilience in overcoming adversity. Educators and support staff should foster environments that promote resilience-building skills and empower students to navigate challenges effectively. Thirdly, the importance of familial support in alleviating emotional distress emphasizes the need for collaboration between schools and families. Educators can facilitate communication with parents and guardians to ensure a supportive network is in place for pregnant and parenting students. Lastly, the student's focus on the well-being of her unborn child underscores the interconnectedness of maternal and educational responsibilities. Schools should adopt policies and practices that accommodate the needs

of pregnant students, ensuring they can fulfil their academic goals while prioritizing their health and that of their children.

This was related to the case study investigated by Pogoy, et. al (2014), which determined the lived experiences of early pregnancy among high and low-performing students in terms of the causes, effects, challenges, and coping mechanisms. Results showed that curiosity, lack of sexual knowledge, financial and family problems, and uncontrolled emotions cause pregnancy among teenagers. Teenage mothers face a lot of challenges after pregnancy like providing proper care and the needs of their child. High-performing teenage mothers are in college levels and work for a living to support the needs of their children. Low-performing teenage mothers ended up as housewives. Teenage mothers have less possibility to finish their studies after engaging in early pregnancy. Taking care of the baby and providing financial assistance are challenges they encountered and tried to cope up with. The academic performance, financial status, and support of the family of teenage mothers determine if they can pursue their studies and achieve their dreams in life. Thus, Bah (2016), supported this from a qualitative study about teenage pregnancy: teenage mothers' experiences and perspectives. The findings revealed among other things, teenagers do not only need information and skills about how to abstain from unwanted or unhealthy sexual activity; they also need to receive accurate, balanced, age-appropriate information about sexuality and sexual behaviour. They need open discussions and to hear up-to-date and consistent messages about responsible sexual behaviour, including information about contraception before they become sexually active. Furthermore, able to develop the required skills in communication and sexual decision-making so that sex does not "just happen. "Experiences manifest that teenage pregnancy and childbearing is not less a monolithic problem, but one with different causes and consequences. Acceptance and social support are critical in helping teenage mothers acquire problem-solving skills that they can apply over their life span to enable them to survive, develop, and achieve success, which enhances coping and adaptation to teenage pregnancy, childbearing, and motherhood.

In Table 5, insights into the behaviours and beliefs of the student, derived from her personal experiences during early pregnancy, are presented. Through the analysis of codes and themes, the researchers aim to elucidate perspectives that may offer valuable insights to others. Below are excerpts from the participant's statements obtained during individual interview.

"Okay, sa mga students nga dili pregnant ano--- paningkamot jud mo nga maka top mo (nikatawa) paningkamot mo na maka---ma enjoy pa ninyo inyong life, makabonding pa mo with friends, maka kanang---- makaapil-apil mo laing activities sa school, mga sports activities maka--- aron nga kana inyong time malaan ninyo ana nga kuan kay puhon nga kamo nasad ana (ningisi) kuan... kamo nasad ang--- muabot man gud ang time nga magminyo mo inyong time matunga jud dili lang jud... dili lang jud pirme mainyuha ang mga gusto nga--- mag ano mo mag party, mag uban sa friends ana or mag-apil mog mga activities kaha karon ug ga school pamo ana tapos.... mao rato (ningisi) (To those students who are not pregnant, stive hard to enjoy life you can still bond with friends, you can still join different activities in school, sports activities, so that

when the time comes when you get married your time will really be divided, you cannot party, go out with friends, join activities anytime you want.)”

“Padayon lang gihapon, katong mga preggy diha nga mga students padayon lang gihapon mo ayaw mo kawala ug hope (ningisi) kay taas pa man kayong panahon inig human padayon gihapon diba? di ta musuko uy (nag ngisi) kanang bisan naglisod dapat padayon lang gihapon, think positive lang japon, wala na saimuhang huna-huna ang mga storya sa uban dapat dili na ninyo e mind kay maka ma stress ramo ana unya ma apektuhan sad ang inyong baby saiyahang pagdako sad sa tiyan maapektuhan siya if gapalabi mog stress tapos e treasure nalang ninyo ng ana preggy mog sayo kay dali raman gihapon ang panahon kay puhon mudako na inyong baby puhon mura ra japon ninyog igsuon, ma--- mura ra ninyog barkada inyong baby so kuan lang na ron kanang bisan naglisod ka karon puhon... ano baya suffered now enjoy later baya (nagngisi)(To those pregnant students, just keep going and don't lose hope, because you still have a long way to go, you can still go on right? We should not be angry, even if its hard, just keep going, think positive, don't mind what other people say, because that will just cause stress, and it will affect you baby. The baby's growth will also be affected when you stress over things, just treasure being pregnant, because time really moves fast, time will come your child will be like a sibling, like a friend when they grow up, so if you are having a hard time, soon as what they said, suffer now, enjoy later.”

The codes, including validating symptoms through online searches, advocating for fellow students to embrace life's opportunities fully before parenthood, providing guidance to non-pregnant peers on preparing for potential future responsibilities, and acknowledging religious objections to abortion, illuminate how the participant's behaviours such as seeking information and demonstrating empathy shape her decision-making and outlook on life. Furthermore, her emphasis on religious convictions regarding abortion underscores the significance of faith in navigating challenging circumstances, ultimately leading her to embrace her situation with acceptance.

These findings hold significant implications for both individuals facing similar circumstances and professionals working in related fields. Understanding how personal behaviours and beliefs influence decision-making during early pregnancy can inform support strategies tailored to the needs of young mothers-to-be. By recognizing the importance of information-seeking and empathy in shaping perspectives, interventions can be designed to empower individuals with accurate information while fostering a supportive environment that acknowledges their unique experiences and beliefs. Moreover, the participant's acknowledgment of religious beliefs regarding abortion highlights the importance of cultural and religious sensitivity in providing comprehensive reproductive health care and support services. Professionals in healthcare, education, and counselling should be equipped with the knowledge and skills to address diverse

religious perspectives sensitively and respectfully, ensuring that individuals feel understood and supported in their decisions.

Conclusions

This study provided a comprehensive exploration of the impacts, challenges, and coping strategies of overcoming stigma of teenage pregnancy while continuing her life as a whole. Through in-depth interviews, thematic analysis, and the triangulation method, valuable insights were gained into different factors contributing to early pregnancy, the challenges faced by pregnant students, and the implications for their education and well-being.

The findings revealed that teenage pregnancy was associated with five transformative impacts in terms of family and social, education and health, physical, emotional and mental health, and behavioural and beliefs. These contributed to the occurrence of early pregnancies but also shaped the experiences of pregnant students, impacting their academic performance, emotional well-being, and social interactions.

This study highlights a unique situation in which a student's pregnancy resulted in a positive effect due to the supportive nature of her family. While teenage pregnancy is often associated with challenges and negative outcomes a common stigma, but this particular case demonstrates the significance of a strong support system in reducing the potential adverse consequences. The study underscores the crucial role that family support plays in shaping the experiences of young mothers-to-be. The unwavering support not only helped alleviate the stress and anxiety typically associated with teenage pregnancy but also contributed to improved overall well-being for both the student and her unborn child.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that while this case study highlights the positive impact of family support on a pregnant student's well-being, each situation is unique, and the outcomes may vary. While teenage pregnancy is often stigmatized and met with judgment or criticism, this situation demonstrates the powerful impact of a supportive and accepting social environment. Another important point highlighted by the study was the importance of school-based reproductive health education and strong parent-daughter relationships in addressing the challenges of teenage pregnancy. By empowering students with knowledge about sexual health, contraception, and healthy relationships, and fostering supportive environments both at home and in school, the risks associated with teenage pregnancy could be mitigated, and the overall well-being of adolescent girls promoted.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations can be made to address the challenges of teenage pregnancy among students: First, there is a need to implement comprehensive reproductive health education. Schools should incorporate comprehensive and age-appropriate reproductive health education into their curriculum.

This education should cover topics such as contraception, STI prevention, healthy relationships, and pregnancy prevention strategies.

Second, it is crucial to strengthen parent-daughter relationships. Parents play a crucial role in supporting their daughters' sexual health and well-being. Programs and initiatives should be developed to promote open communication between parents and daughters about sexual health topics. Parenting workshops and resources can provide parents with the knowledge and tools to discuss sensitive issues with their children and offer support when needed.

Third, providing accessible support services is essential. Schools and communities should ensure that pregnant students have access to a range of support services, including counselling, healthcare, and academic assistance. Pregnant students may face unique challenges that require specialized support, such as childcare assistance, flexible academic accommodations, and emotional support. These services should be readily available and easily accessible to meet the diverse needs of pregnant students.

Fourth, fostering a supportive school environment is key. Schools should strive to create a supportive and inclusive environment where pregnant students feel valued and supported. This can be achieved through implementing anti-discrimination policies, providing peer support groups for pregnant students, and offering resources to help them navigate the challenges of pregnancy while continuing their education.

Fifth, by involving multiple stakeholders, it becomes possible to develop holistic strategies that encompass educational, social, and cultural aspects. Engaging stakeholders can also help in raising awareness, reducing stigma, and implementing evidence-based interventions that effectively prevent teenage pregnancy and support pregnant students.

Lastly, extending the research by conducting a comparative study involving multiple cases to gain a broader understanding of the determinants of teenage pregnancy. By examining various contexts and demographics, researchers can identify commonalities and differences in factors influencing teenage pregnancy. This comparative analysis can provide valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of teenage pregnancy and help tailor interventions to specific populations.

By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can work together to address the complex challenges of teenage pregnancy and support the educational success and well-being of pregnant students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers used a purposive sampling in selecting a relevant participant for the study. It was a non-probability sampling method commonly used in research to select participants or cases based on specific criteria that align with the research objectives.

Purposive sampling focused on selecting individuals or cases that possessed certain characteristics or qualities relevant to the study.

In this study, the selection of a participant met the following criteria: A participant with the aged 16 years old, a student currently enrolled to Junior High Curriculum and she has an experience to teenage pregnancy. Based on the established criteria, the researchers identified this potential participant who matched the desired characteristics. This can be done through various means, such as consulting with schools, educational institutions, relevant organizations, or community leaders who could help identify eligible individual were contacted.

The researchers began by obtaining the necessary permissions and consent to conduct the research by sending a permit letter to the School Principal of Malaybalay City National Science High School, seeking approval to conduct the study on their premises. Additionally, a consent letter for interview questions and the potential use of audio or video recording during the interviews will be sent to both the students and their parents. This letter provided detailed information about the purpose of the research, the benefits, and the procedures involved. It emphasized the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants, assuring them that their personal information would be protected. The researchers explicitly stated that participation was voluntary, and participants had the right to withdraw at any time without consequences.

Once the necessary approvals and consents were obtained, the researchers proceeded to orient the participant about the data-gathering procedure by providing a clear explanation of the flow of the interview process and ensure that the participants understand the purpose of the study and their role in it. During the interview, the researchers administered the carefully designed interview questions to the student, focusing on capturing her experiences with teenage pregnancy. The researchers created a supportive and comfortable environment to encourage open and honest sharing of experiences.

Acknowledgments

First and foremost, our sincere thanks to the School Principal of Malaybalay City National Science High School (MCNSHS) for granting permission to conduct this study and for providing an environment conducive to learning and research.

Our heartfelt appreciation to Prof. Cherly C. Cordova, our qualitative data analysis professor, whose guidance, insights, and encouragement were invaluable throughout this journey. Her expertise shaped the direction of this study and deepened my understanding of qualitative research methods.

We would also like to extend my deepest appreciation to the board of panel Dr. Jennyliza T. Uchang and Dr. Denis A. Tan for their insightful corrections and suggestions.

Their critical feedback helped refine and strengthen this research, ensuring its quality and accuracy.

We also deeply thankful to the student and her parent for their willingness and enthusiasm in participating in this study. Their cooperation and support were vital to the success of this research.

We would like to acknowledge our family for their unwavering love, patience, and support.

Lastly, we would like to express our deepest gratitude to God Almighty for His guidance and blessings throughout the course of this study.

REFERENCES

- Bah, Y. M. (2016). Teenage Pregnancy: Teenage Mothers' Experiences and Perspectives: A Qualitative study. *Journal of Health, Medicine and Nursing*, 29, 118–136.
<https://iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JHMN/article/download/32668/33559>
- Maemeko, E., Nkengbeza, D. and Chokomosi, T. (2018) The Impact of Teenage Pregnancy on Academic Performance of Grade 7 Learners at a School in the Zambezi Region. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 6, 88-100. doi: 10.4236/jss.2018.69006
- Mathewos, S., & Mekuria, A. (2018). Teenage Pregnancy and Its Associated Factors among School Adolescents of Arba Minch Town, Southern Ethiopia. *Ethiopian journal of health sciences*, 28(3), 287–298. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ejhs.v28i3.6>
- Merriam, S.B. (2009). *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- National Nutrition Council. (2016). Sounding the alarm on teenage pregnancy in the Philippines. <http://www.fnri.dost.gov.ph/>
- Nettle, D., Dickins, T. E., Coall, D. A., & Davies, P. M. (2013). Patterns of physical and psychological development in future teenage mothers. *Evolution, Medicine and Public Health*, 2013(1), 187–196. <https://doi.org/10.1093/emph/eot016>
- Pogoy, A. M., Verzosa, R., Coming, N. S., & Agustino, R. G. (2014). Lived Experiences of Early Pregnancy Among Teenagers: A Phenomenological Study Lived Experiences of Early Pregnancy Among Teenagers: A Phenomenological Study, 10(2). <http://eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/viewFile/2587/2448>
- Tabei, K., Cuisia-Cruz, E. S. S., Smith, C., & Seposo, X. (2021). Association between Teenage Pregnancy and Family Factors: An Analysis of the Philippine National Demographic and Health Survey 2017. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*, 9(12), 1720. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9121720>
- United Nations Children's Fund (2022). Adolescent Health and Well- Being data. <http://data.unicef.org/topic/adolescents/>
- World Health Organization (2024). Adolescent Sexual Reproductive Health. <https://www.who.int/southeastasia/activities/adolescent-sexual-reproductive-health>

